

Sakuranetin monomethyl ether (m.p. 116-117°) and sakuranetin oxime (m.p. 201-203°), prepared from this sample were identical in all respects with the derivatives of an authentic sample of sakuranetin.

The filtrate after hydrolysis gave on treatment with phenylhydrazine acetate, as usual, glucosazone (m.p. 205-206°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of glucosazone).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 7, 1950.

A NOTE ON PERIODATES OF CADMIUM

BY SURJIT SINGH AND APPAR SINGH

The following periodates of cadmium are reported in literature :

1. Secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO_5 .
2. Cadmium metaperiodate, $\text{Cd}(\text{IO}_3)_2$.
3. Trihydrated cadmium diparaperiodate, $\text{Cd}_4 \text{I}_2 \text{O}_{11}, 3\text{H}_2 \text{O}$.
4. Pantahydrated cadmium mesoperiodate, $\text{Cd}_3 (\text{IO}_5)_2, 5\text{H}_2 \text{O}$.
5. Ennehydrated cadmium dimesoperiodate, $\text{Cd}_2 \text{I}_2 \text{O}_9, 9\text{H}_2 \text{O}$.

Out of the five periodates of cadmium only two were found to be formed, viz., secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO_5 , and hexahydrated cadmium mesoperiodate, $\text{Cd}_3 (\text{IO}_5)_2, 6\text{H}_2 \text{O}$, as described below.

Secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO_5 , was prepared by adding an excess of a hot solution of periodic acid to a warm suspension of cadmium carbonate in water. The excess of the acid was ensured by litmus paper. The mixture was stirred and kept hot till there was no effervescence. A fine gelatinous precipitate was formed which turned granular on standing. It was filtered, washed with water till free from the acid and then dried at 60° in a hot air-oven. It was analysed as follows.

The cadmium content of the periodate was determined by the pyridine method (Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis," 1946, p. 510).

The percentage of iodine in the periodate was found by Kimmins' method as modified by Bahl and Partington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088).

Available oxygen was estimated by the method adopted by Bahl and Partington (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

No.	%Cd.	%I ₂ .	%Available O ₂
1.	35.10	40.07	18.00
2.	35.12	40.00	17.90
3.	35.20	40.00	17.90

The above results agree with the formula of the secondary cadmium mesoperiodate, CdHIO₅. The calculated values being, Cd, 35.0%; I₂, 39.7% and available oxygen according to the decomposition, $2\text{CdHIO}_5 \rightarrow 2\text{CdO} + \text{I}_2 + 3\text{O}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$, is 17.60%.

Hexahydrated cadmium mesoperiodate, Cd₃(IO₅)₂, 6H₂O was prepared by the addition of a hot solution of secondary sodium paraperiodate in dilute nitric acid or a hot solution of potassium metaperiodate in water to an excess of cadmium sulphate with constant stirring. The mixture was boiled for some time to ensure the completion of the reaction. The insoluble periodate formed was filtered, washed free of the soluble salts with water, and dried at 60° in a hot air-oven. It was analysed as above.

TABLE II

A				B			
No.	%Cd.	%I ₂ .	%AvailableO ₂	No.	%Cd.	%I ₂ .	%AvailableO ₂
1.	39.20	29.60	12.90	1.	39.20	29.60	12.95
2.	39.48	29.40	12.09	2.	39.32	29.40	13.12
3.	39.70	29.18	13.01	3.	39.18	29.12	13.10

Calc. for Cd₃(IO₅)₂, 6H₂O : Cd, 39.16 ; I₂, 29.14 ; available oxygen, 13.05%.

The authors wish to offer their sincere thanks to S. Sachdev Singh, Head of the Chemistry Dept., Govt. College, Ludhiana for affording all the facilities for doing the above work.

